

An Empirical Study of Attitude towards Entrepreneurial Intention among Pakistan and China Agricultural Graduates in Agribusiness

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Abstract: The purpose of this paper is to investigate the difference of attitudes towards entrepreneurial intention (EI) of Agricultural graduates in agribusiness, this cannot be realized without harnessing the quality human resource base of the youth, especially graduates from agricultural faculties, Pakistani and Chinese Agri-students used to identify the possible differences between potential entrepreneurs from these distinct national contexts.

The data includes set of agricultural universities being surveyed (n= 640) was collected in 2016. The Descriptive and Binary Logistic Regression was employed in order to analyze through SPSS 25.00 to examine the effect of individual's attitudes on EI in agribusiness, independent variables include individual's perceived capabilities, the ability to recognize business opportunities, entrepreneurial network, risk perceptions as well as range of socio-cultural attitudes. The findings support the relationship between an individual's attitudes and their entrepreneurial intention. Individual's capability, opportunity recognition, networks and range of socio-cultural perceptions all influence EI significantly also, age, gender, the educational background of students, media motivation and attention, self-realization status, practical agricultural experience and risks perception were found to have a significant influence on students' intention to take up agribusiness as a source of future self-employment avenue upon graduation.

Keywords: Entrepreneurial Intention, China, Pakistan, Attitude, Opportunities, Self-efficacy, Risk perception
Entrepreneurial network, Status, Agribusiness, University Graduates

I. Introduction

Currently, changes in the world economies created copious problems, the entrepreneurship or self-employment the best to solve the unemployment problems of graduates come to this issue in the huge populous countries like China and Pakistan. Self-employment in agribusiness value chains and market linkages are terms that are being used more and more when talking about agriculture and farming this offers many setbacks to both individual and economy as whole to boost small agribusiness of labor demands. (Pejvak, Marie-Louise, Kaveh, & Phillip). An agribusiness has been defined as all business-oriented entities involved in the production, input supply, agro-processing, marketing and distribution of

agricultural commodities to flourish in market's economy is arguably the largest source of employment among rural populates in many developing countries (FAO,2014)

To deal with issues that have too often been discussed in terms of false dichotomy the diversity among the nation in their physical endowment, cultural-historical context precludes any universally applicable definition of the role that agriculture should play in the process of economic growth and development. Typically, 50 to 60 percent of national income is produced in agriculture and from 60 to 80 percent labor force directly or indirectly engaged with agriculture or agribusiness. Despite this, there is a divergence in both countries now face daunting employment problems. China and Pakistan appear to be increasingly vulnerable to rising inequality, slower job creation, and shrinking farm sizes, suggesting that governments need to refocus on integrating lagging regions into an increasingly high effective tool for job creation and poverty reduction.

In the national development agenda, agriculture is expected to lead the growth and structural transformation of the economy; providing jobs, ensuring food security and producing the needed raw materials to propel the country's economy (George, 2008). Significant improvements in the productivity of the agriculture sector are required to raise the average real incomes of both countries thereby reducing poverty and providing job security and sustainable rural livelihood (FAO, 2014).

Entrepreneurial Intention (EI) is generally believed to be the single most relevant predictor of entrepreneurial behavior is the first step in an intensive process of venture creation. Empirical researches show that becoming an entrepreneur is a risky decision since they need to cope with an uncertainty. Moreover, more risk-averse persons are less likely to become entrepreneurs. However, risk perception is not a only one psychological variable influencing the decision to become an entrepreneur. (Ács & Audretsch) argued that risk perception differ from person to person and risk perception connected with certain decisions are lower when people have more experience, higher capabilities or more knowledge in their self-employment field. Based on the theory of planned behavior (TPB), individual behavior is driven by behavioral intentions where behavioral intentions are a function of an individual's attitude toward the behavior, subjective norms surrounding the performance of the behavior, and the individual's perceived behavioral control (Ajzen). Theory of Planned Behavior (TPB) developed by Ajzen in 1991 to explain that entrepreneurial intention is influenced by three perception factors; namely, personal attraction to entrepreneurial activity, perceived subjective norms, and perceived behavioral control or self-efficacy applied by (Krueger & Carsrud).

An entrepreneur is passionate about growing his business and is constantly looking for new opportunities. Entrepreneurs are also innovators. They always look for better and more efficient and profitable ways to do things. Being innovative is an important quality for an agribusiness, especially when the business faces strong competition or operates in a rapidly changing environment (FAO, 2012). An entrepreneur is someone who produces for the market and is a determined and creative leader, always looking for opportunities to improve and expand his business. An entrepreneur likes to take calculated risks and assumes responsibility for both profits and losses.

Development of agriculture cannot be realized without harnessing the quality human resource base of the youth, especially graduates from agricultural faculties. Universities are the places where new products and processes, that lay and consolidate the foundation of new firms and enterprises, are created. More specifically, university graduate students are the most promising sources of entrepreneurship (Veciana, Aponte, & Urbano). The differences between Chinese and Pakistani agricultural students on entrepreneurial intention were compared the entrepreneurial intention of university students in both countries has identified. The purpose of this paper is to investigate the to what extent attitudinal influence of perceptions toward entrepreneurial intention in agribusiness through a comparative study among Chinese and Pakistani agricultural graduates.

II. Literature Review

2.1. Entrepreneurial Intention

Individuals who are perceived to have a lack of knowledge finance are less probably to have the entrepreneurial intention (Shinnar, Giacomini, & Janssen). Entrepreneurial intentions are the first step in an intensive

process of venture creation which are the necessary precursor to entrepreneurial behaviors (Koçoğlu & Hassan). An entrepreneur is a person who starts a business and has a great imagination, flexibility, creativeness for business an individual can intend to become an entrepreneur when the expectation of the entrepreneurship is pleasurable, gaining freedom, risky, the work is hard and the income is high. (Venesaar, Kolbre, & Piliste).

There have been the previous studies to show the evidence of reasons people choosing to become entrepreneurs rather than employees such as desires of freedom, self-controlling, and potential affluent (Liñán, Santos, & Fernández). The researches concerning with the entrepreneurial intention have focused on the psychological and social factor influencing and driving people to become entrepreneurs.

Entrepreneurial Intention defined as the search for information that can be used to help fulfill the goal of venture creation (Krueger Jr, Reilly, & Carsrud). An entrepreneurial intention as a state of mind that people wish to create a new firm or a new value driver inside existing organizations to starting a new business is a process with a planning rather than impulsive decision-making defined by (Rueda, Moriano, & Liñán). (Krueger Jr et al.) also stated that a person who has a potential to start a new business or sees a good business opportunity might choose not to start his business if he lacks an entrepreneurial intention. The entrepreneurial intention is influenced by three perception factors; namely, personal attraction to entrepreneurial activity, the first one is an attitude (or personal attitude) which indicates the degree to which an individual has a positive or negative personal concern regarding the intended behavior. It refers to "the attractiveness of the proposed behavior in a positive or negative degree of a personal valuation to become an entrepreneur" (Pejvak et al.). The second is subjective norms which measure the perceived social support of performing (or not performing) the intended behavior. Influential People (parents, friends, etc.), or reference, serve as reference guides to behavior and influence the beliefs of subjective norms (Gird & Bagraim). The final one is perceived behavioral control known as self-efficacy which associates an individual's perception of the ease or severity of the intended behavior.

Perceived subjective norms, and Perceived behavioral control or self-efficacy (Krueger & Carsrud). The relationship between entrepreneurship and risk perception has received some attention from researchers who have considered the relationship between entrepreneurial decisions and risk aversion. Risk perception or fear of failure is an important variable to have a negative influence to start a new business. A reduced perception of the likelihood of failure should increase the probability that an individual will start a new business (Arenius & Minniti). Risk perception is also an important factor influencing entrepreneurial intention (Simon, Houghton, & Aquino). There is a direct relationship between risk perception and entrepreneurial intention according to (Wagner). Fear of failure is recognized as one of the barriers to pursue entrepreneurship (Lüthje & Franke) stated that reducing the fear of failure's perception should increase the probability that an individual will start a new business.

2.2. Culture and entrepreneurship intention in agribusiness

Cultural context can shape entrepreneurial attitudes and intentions in the past research suggested by (Shinnar et al.). That culture shapes individual behavior state that cultural factor is one of the factors influencing individual's career choice to be an entrepreneur and create a new business. (Liñán & Fernandez-Serrano) revealed that Cross-cultural studies are needed for the effect of different cultures and values on the entrepreneurial intention to be better understood. According to (Hofstede), Hofstede's four dimensions of individualism (IDV), uncertainty avoidance (UA), power distance (PD), and masculinity (MAS) are proposed to cluster Nations based on the difference of culture. Several researchers call for an examination of entrepreneurial intentions across different nations and cultures.

Entrepreneurship education program has affected student behavior control and anticipation of positive and negative impacts this research shows that educational background in agriculture is highly affecting entrepreneurship intention in the agricultural aspect. (Tateh, Latip, & Awang Marikan) identifies correlation analysis indicated that youth entrepreneurial intentions are positively correlated to their personality traits (risk-taking propensity, innovativeness, and tolerance of ambiguity), and social learning (knowledge and experience and family upbringing) (Movahedi, Latifi, & Sayyar) stated a motive of a bachelor candidate to work in the agricultural sector. Hence, this entrepreneurial intention tends to be prominently dominated by agriculture graduates.

Respondents with agriculture background are more likely to become Agri-entrepreneurs compared to the ones with social science backgrounds. (Mohamed, Rezai, Nasir Shamsudin, & Mu'az Mahmud). Results of the analysis found students' perception regarding the prospects of agribusiness enterprises in Ghana to have a statistical significant

influence at both 1 and 5 percent levels of significance on students’ intention to take up agribusiness as a future self-employment avenue (Zakaria, Adam, & Abujaja). However, it is contrasted with research conducted by (Abdullah & Sulaiman) on youth interests in agricultural entrepreneurship which shows that knowledge and education background is not significantly affecting those youths to be entrepreneurs.

The agricultural sector is less favorable for many young people and they are not willing to choose organic agriculture as their carrier of work (Utsugi). Research expresses that those people consider working in organic agriculture especially as financial factors needed to determine that organic agriculture is able to make a decent living or not. There is no more different with researches conducted by (Boateng, Boateng, & Bampoe)

The financial condition tends neither capital lack nor business return causing hampered entrepreneurship of the youths Ahmed et al. and (Azwar); agricultural sector assessed has a high risk so that investment and return are being a sensitive issue recently. Many young agricultural graduates tend to do business in other sectors (Parcell & Sykuta). This condition attains to become a research reference where agriculture is less interested because of financial problems. Financial support to some participants should be responsible for the youth entrepreneurial crisis in the agricultural sector which is later parallel with entrepreneur’s intention of agriculture. (Ridha & Wahyu). The youth perceive lack of capitals, skills, supports, market opportunities and risks to be main obstacles for intending entrepreneurship.

In this study, we draw the conceptual framework and research questions as the following; (1) used by Wilert Puriwat and Suchart Tripopsakulin (2015) inspired us to study this pattern. As it is shown in figure whether a range of cognitive perceptions and their respective effect on individual’s intent to start a new venture differ in Chinese and Pakistan university graduates. The predictors or independent variables in this study are individual’s cognitive perceptions; whereas, the entrepreneurial intention is criterion dependent variable.

Figure1 Conceptual framework of the study

III. Research Methodology

3.1. Sample Description

The sample in this study was obtained in questionnaires consist of some cognitive items that may allow analyzing entrepreneurial intentions. Data collection process was completed by a self-administered questionnaire from students of Huazhong Agricultural University (HZAU) and Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam (SAU) students in various agriculture schools. The questionnaire was first designed into English and then carefully translated into Chinese

to be pretested and provided to be both compressive and clear. The empirical analysis includes a primary data of two agricultural universities being surveyed (N = 640) which was collected in 2016. The students were in the 1st, 2nd, 3rd and 4th-grade year of their study with 30.3 % female and 69.7% male student from Chinese University 37.5% male and 62.5% female student respectively from Pakistani university. Binary Logistic regression used to investigate the effect of individual's attitudes on Entrepreneurial Intention (EI) Independent variables include individual's perceived capabilities, the ability to recognize business opportunities, self-efficacy, desirable career, entrepreneurial network, risk perceptions as well as a range of socio-cultural attitudes. Moreover, a cross-cultural comparison of the model is conducted among Pakistani and Chinese agricultural university graduates' students.

3.2. Model Development

This study tries to identify significant variables that assist estimate the probability of an individual expressing intention to start an agribusiness after graduation (entrepreneurial intention). The specific variables used to measure concepts developed in the theory section are the following

3.2.1. Dependent variable: Entrepreneurial intention: In the questionnaire section, the question asked "Whether they intend to start an agribusiness? (0=No, 1=Yes)" is used to represent the entrepreneurial intention construct in the conceptual model.

3.2.2. Independent Variables

- 1 Perception on opportunities recognition in doing new agribusiness: The question "Would be good opportunities to start a firm in the area where you live in? (0=No, 1=Yes)" is used to measure the perception of opportunities construct.
- 2 Perception on self-efficacy (Independent variable): The question "Do you believe you have the required skill and knowledge (capability perception) to start an agribusiness? (0=No, 1=Yes)" is used to measure the perception of self-efficacy.
- 3 Perception of fear of failure: The question "Whether fear of failure (risk perception) would prevent you from setting up an agribusiness or not? (0=No, 1=Yes)" is used to measure the perception of fear of failure.
- 4 Perception on Entrepreneurial networks: The question "Whether you personally know someone who had started an agribusiness in your area? (0=No, 1=Yes)" is used to measure the entrepreneurial network.

3.2.3. Control Variables

Control variables such as gender, age, farming experience, agribusiness experience, family income, the current status of education, expected degree (undergraduate, master graduates, philosophy graduates and doctoral graduates) and major discipline in agriculture in order to clarify the relationship between entrepreneurial intention and a range of cognitive perceptions. The binary logistic regression model is a logistic regression that applies to dichotomous. Binary logistic regression is used to predict and model binary problems in many fields. The reason logistic regression is preferred by many researchers is that it allows one to see the effect every variable has on the model. The binary logistic regression model estimates the probability that an individual belongs to a certain group (dependent=1), or not (independent=0). It also identifies the most important variables explaining the differences in both groups. Additionally, the models do not make assumptions about the statistical distribution of the variables. In this study, the use of the binary logistic regression model would be reasonable on three conditions; namely, the dependent and independent variables are dichotomous, and the effect of a certain level of the independent variables on the probability that the studied event is present can be measured.

IV. Results

Table 1 Sample Distribution by Region

			Gender		Total
			Male	Female	
Nationality	Chinese	N	120	200	320
		%	37.5	62.5	100.0
	Pakistani	N	223	97	320
		%	69.7	30.3	100.0
Total		N	343	297	640
		%	53.6	46.4	100.0

The entrepreneurial intention is measured by the question of intention to start an agribusiness after graduation (Yes/No) and the sample distribution by region. Table 1 Are you personally intend to start an agribusiness in your area?

Table 2 Entrepreneurial Intent of Samples

Entrepreneurial Intention	Cultural Difference	Chinese		Pakistani		Total
	Yes	256	80.00%	241	75.31%	497
No	64	20.00%	79	24.69%	143	
Total	320	100.00%	320	100.00%	640	

The questionnaires were distributed in two agricultural universities, one in China, Huazhong Agricultural University (HZAU) and one in the Pakistan, Sindh Agriculture University Tandojam (SAU) The university graduates were asked question they personally intend to start an agribusiness in your area? Result found significant response from both sides of graduates 80% in China and more than 75% in Pakistan answered positively if opportunities and chances are favorable they preferred and willing to start up new agribusiness after graduation but a few respondents' denials answered approximately 25% from Pakistan and 20% from Chinese graduate due to their dependents on family. A brief overview of the distribution of the samples is shown in Table 2

Summary of the respondents' age, gender, farming experience, agribusiness experience, family income (000) current status in education expected degree and major agriculture discipline and other factors used in this research study presents in Table 3. The structure of gender was 53.6% male (N = 343) and 46.4% female (N=297) students, while students participated from HZAU 120 (37.5%) male, 200 (62.5%) female and from SAU 223 (69.7 %) male, 97 (30.3%) female graduates participants contributed in the survey. The age composition remained (11.1%, <20), (49.8%, 21-25) (29.1%, 26-30) (9.4%, 31-35) >35 (0.6%) in years.

Hence farming experience mean was 1.85, agribusiness experience means 2.18, monthly family income means remains 1.85. The current status of participants means 1.85 whereas 16.3%, first-year student, 15.8% fourth year, 30.5% and third year 37.5% second year respectively were studying in their respective universities, while students have interviewed master of philosophy graduates (2.5%), doctoral graduates (12.8%) master graduates (28.4%) respectively the maximum participation was from undergraduate students (56.3%) hence the mean 1.71, for expected degree, and mean 8.26, for the graduates' who were studying in agriculture majoring in both universities presented in Table 3

Table 3 Descriptive Analysis

		N	Mean	Std. Dev.
Gender	Male	343 (53.6%)	1.46	0.50
	Female	297 (46.4%)		
Age (Years)	<20	71 (11.1%)	2.39	0.83
	21-25	319 (49.8%)		
	26-30	186 (29.1%)		
	31-35	60 (9.4%)		
	>35	4(0.6%)		
Farming Experience (Years)	<1	409 (63.91%)	1.85	1.31
	1-4	67(10.5%)		
	5-10	67(10.5%)		
	11-15	47(7.3%)		
	>15	50(7.8%)		
Agribusiness Experience (Years)	<1	333 (52.0%)	2.18	1.44
	1-4	77(12.0%)		
	5-10	81(12.7%)		
	11-15	82(12.8%)		
	>15	67(10.5%)		
Family Income (000)	<10,	141 (22.0%)	2.21	0.99
	10-15	320 (50.0%)		
	16-20	101 (15.8%)		
	21-25	58(9.1%)		
	>25	20 (3.1%)		
Current Status	1 st Year	104 (16.3%)	2.46	0.94
	2 nd Year	240(37.5%)		
	3 rd Year	195 (30.5%)		
	4 th Year	101 (15.8%)		
Expected Degree	Under Graduate (Bachelor)	360 (56.3%)	1.719	1.01
	Master Graduate (Sophomore)	182 (28.4%)		
	Master of Philosophy (M.Phil.)	16(2.5%)		
	Doctoral Graduate (Ph.D.)	82 (12.8%)		
Major Discipline in Agriculture	General Agriculture	52 (8.1%)	8.26	5.26
	Agricultural Economics & Management	85 (13.3%)		
	Agricultural Engineering	24(3.8%)		
	Animal Sciences	57(8.9%)		
	Life Sciences & Technology	36(5.6%)		
	Agri-Extension Education	24(3.8%)		
	Information Technology	39(6.1%)		
	Plant Sciences & Technology	29(4.5%)		
	Resource Environment & Fisheries	26(4.1%)		
	Soil Sciences	17(2.7%)		
	Horticulture & Forestry Sciences	34(5.3%)		
	Land Resources & Environment	35(5.5%)		
	Humanities & Social Sciences	39(6.1%)		
	Public Administration	23(3.6%)		
Others	92(14.4%)			

Table 4 represents the sequence of the binary logistic regression analysis in both Chinese and Pakistani universities. Starting by includes only control variables in Model 1, Model 2 includes three more variables: perception on the opportunity, perception on capability (self-efficacy) and perception entrepreneurial network. Model 3 added up the risk perception (fear of failure). Model 4 comprises three additional variables; desirable career, media motivation, self-respect.

Table 4 Binary Logistic Regression on Entrepreneurial Intention

Variables	Model-1			Model -2			Model -3			Model -4		
	B	Sig.	Exp(B)	B	Sig.	Exp(B)	B	Sig.	Exp(B)	B	Sig.	Exp(B)
Constant	1.71*	0.00	5.54	0.60*	0.36	1.82	0.59*	0.36	1.81	0.58*	0.44	1.78
Gender	0.15*	0.48	1.16	0.21*	0.33	1.24	0.21*	0.33	1.24	0.22*	0.34	1.25
Age	-0.48*	0.01	0.62	-0.48*	0.02	0.62	-0.46*	0.02	0.63	-0.46*	0.02	0.63
Farming Experience	-0.09*	0.19	0.91	-0.07*	0.32	0.93	-0.07*	0.32	0.93	-0.07*	0.31	0.93
Agribusiness Experience	-0.01*	0.86	0.99	-0.02*	0.83	0.99	-0.01*	0.84	0.99	-0.02*	0.83	0.98
Family Income	0.05*	0.67	1.05	0.02*	0.85	1.02	0.02*	0.88	1.02	0.01*	0.91	1.01
Current Status	0.16*	0.13	1.17	0.15*	0.20	1.16	0.14*	0.23	1.15	0.14*	0.23	1.15
Expected Degree	0.18*	0.22	1.19	0.14*	0.36	1.15	0.12*	0.43	1.13	0.12*	0.44	1.12
Major discipline	-0.01*	0.48	0.99	-0.01*	0.67	0.99	-0.01*	0.58	0.99	-0.01*	0.60	0.99
Opportunities Recognition				0.30*	0.18	1.35	0.25*	0.28	1.28	0.24*	0.29	1.28
Entrepreneurial Network				0.61*	0.01	1.85	0.60*	0.01	1.82	0.60*	0.01	1.83
Risk Perception				0.98*	0.00	2.66	0.98*	0.00	2.67	0.99*	0.00	2.68
Self-Efficacy							0.18*	0.42	1.19	0.18*	0.44	1.19
Desirable Career										-0.03*	0.91	0.97
Media Motivation										0.06*	0.77	1.07
Respect & Status										-0.03*	0.89	0.97

levels based on Wald statistics: * significant level p less than 0.5.

In statistics, multicollinearity (also called collinearity) is a phenomenon with the help of which two or more predictor variables in a multiple regression model can be described as highly correlated, this means the one can be linearly predicted from the others with a substantial degree of accuracy. Multicollinearity helps to describe the high correlations of two or more independent variables. It is used to accurately know the effects of independent variables with the used of regression analysis. The most direct test for multicollinearity is available in linear regression.

So, we examine a multicollinearity problem for testing the influence of a range of cognitive perceptions and their respective effect on individual's intent to start a new venture, the Tolerance and Variance Inflation Factor (VIF) is used to measure the impact of multicollinearity among predictor variables in a binary logistic regression model. The value of VIF less than 2.5 is regarded as indicating no multicollinearity in the model according to Allison (1999), The VIF of the variables ranges from 1.00 to 2.27. It can be seen that the multicollinearity will not cause any problem to the estimation and there is no redundant variable, therefore, there is no multicollinearity problem and the data are suitable for further analysis.

Table 5 Goodness-of-Fit statistics for Models

Goodness of fit Statistics	Model-1	Model- 2	Model- 3	Model- 4
Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients (significant level)	0.10	0.00	0.00	0.00
Nagelkerke R Square	0.03	0.13	0.13	0.14
Cox & Snell R Square	0.02	0.09	0.09	0.09
likelihood	666.630 ^a	621.691 ^a	621.033 ^a	620.908 ^a
Correct Percentage	77.70	76.70	75.60	76.40

* A cut-off value of 0.5

In table 5, the Nagelkerke pseudo R squared shows how well the dependent variable can be explained by independent variables in the model. Nagelkerke pseudo R squared improves from 0.032 to 0.135 and Cox & Snell R Square 0.021 to 0.088 when the variables are added to the model, hence the overall success rate ranges from 75.40. to 77.70 for a correct prediction, the Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients depicts the significant level in all models while likelihood decreased gradually in Model2 to Model4 when adds up more variable.

Table 6 Regional Binary Logistic Regression on Entrepreneurial Intention

Variables	Chinese			Pakistani		
	B	Sig.	Exp(B)	B	Sig.	Exp(B)
Constant	-0.48*	0.66	0.62	0.95*	0.41	2.58
Gender	0.25*	0.46	1.28	0.26*	0.49	1.29
Age	-0.07*	0.84	0.94	-0.76*	0.01	0.47
Farming Experience	-0.05*	0.69	0.95	-0.06*	0.51	0.94
Agribusiness Experience	-0.08*	0.47	0.92	0.04*	0.71	1.04
Family Income	-0.08*	0.67	0.92	-0.02*	0.89	0.98
Current Status	-0.23*	0.20	0.80	0.37*	0.03	1.44
Expected Degree	0.19*	0.53	1.21	0.21*	0.27	1.24
Major discipline	0.05*	0.07	1.05	-0.05*	0.07	0.95
Opportunities Recognition	-0.13*	0.74	0.88	0.15*	0.69	1.16
Entrepreneurial Network	0.36*	0.32	1.43	0.03*	0.93	1.03
Risk Perception	0.02*	0.96	1.02	0.37*	0.26	1.45
Self-Efficacy	1.18*	0.00	3.25	0.18*	0.59	1.19
Desirable Career	0.76*	0.02	2.13	1.16*	0.00	3.17
Media Motivation	0.39*	0.22	1.47	-0.04*	0.91	0.96
Respect & Status	0.55*	0.13	1.74	-0.07*	0.82	0.93

Significance levels based on Wald statistics: * significant level p less than 0.5.

Logistic regression analysis was employed to predict the probability that participants are willing to start their own business. The Model-1 that is the basic model including control variables such as gender, age, farming and agribusiness experience, family income, the current status of education, expected degree from undergraduate, master, and postgraduate and the major discipline in agriculture.

The result shows that all control variables significantly contribute to explaining entrepreneurial intentions (EI) in agribusiness except family income and major discipline in agriculture whereas male versus female entrepreneurship is not just confined to any one gender due to multi-faceted economic pressures around the globe, awareness of female entrepreneurship has increased and is characterized by the increasing numbers of women setting up in business. Where high levels of optimistic expectations regarding their ventures amongst both genders conferring to the odd-ratios, female participants are 279 (46.4%) in a total little bit less likely to male participants 343 (54.6%) to show the entrepreneurial intention in agribusiness. Furthermore, age is associated with lower entrepreneurial intentions since every additional year of age of respondents are associated with decreasing probability to show their entrepreneurial intention in agribusiness.

Model 2 includes two cognitive variables; opportunity recognition and entrepreneurial network it entails the ability to effectively manage to monitor the project, for this reason, individuals' cognitive variables characters such as opportunity recognition entrepreneurial network are significantly associated with higher entrepreneurial intentions with the odd ratio 1.02 and 3.24 respectively.

Model 3 includes risk perception (fear of failure) and self-efficacy into the model graduates who have fear of failure doing business are but going to take risk when engaging an activity related to the probability of success hence the risk

perception remains with odd ratios 1.43 and 0.95 respectively in both countries the entrepreneurs prefer to take moderate risks in their business decisions; they do not like to be involved in situations where there is extreme risk or uncertainty. Therefore, commonsense proposes that entrepreneurs must not be opposed to taking risks. graduates are less likely to have an intention to become entrepreneurs and self-efficacy is also acted risk, therefore, the high level of self-efficacy in both sides of respondents' it is necessary that entrepreneurial characteristics are more likely to have an intention to become entrepreneurs in agribusiness.

Finally, in the socio-cultural perceptions, three other variables are added to Model 4. The result represents that those graduates who have a desirable career, media motivation, and good entrepreneurial status whether being an entrepreneur is valued more than other professions are significantly affect entrepreneurial intentions of individuals' in agribusiness.

Table 7 Goodness-of-fit statistics by Region

	China	Pakistan
Omnibus Tests of Model Coefficients	0.00	0.00
Nagelkerke R Square	0.16	0.20
Cox & Snell R Square	0.10	0.14
likelihood	285.142 ^a	310.540 ^a
Correct Percentage	80.00	75.30

*A cut-off value of 0.5

The logistic regression was performed to test for the existence of significant differences between Chinese and Pakistani agricultural graduates. Overall, the model is significant in both nations, according to the Omnibus test and the predicted correct success rate 75.3% in Pakistani and 80% in Chinese respectively in while Nagelkerke R Square increased and Cox & Snell R Square in Pakistani graduates as compared to Chinese graduates in Table 7.

V. Discussion

The findings supported the relationship between an individual's attitudes and their entrepreneurial intention in agribusiness. Individual's competence, opportunity recognition, determinants of entrepreneurial network and self-efficacy and a range of socio-cultural perceptions all variables influence (EI) significantly.

According to the results of logistic regression, our modeling reveals a significant difference between the Pakistan agriculture university students and their counterparts in China, gender remains significant but perception of opportunities recognition, family income, represents nonsignificant in both university graduates, age, farming work experiences is significant factor in Pakistani graduates only but not significant factor in Chinese students, another significant difference between two countries students agribusiness experience is significant in Chinese students but not Pakistani graduates.

while fear of failure (risk perception) was found to influence EI significantly affect the entrepreneurial intention only in Pakistani students but not significant in Chinese graduates, hence determinants of entrepreneurial network and self-efficacy is found significant in Chinese but non-significant in Pakistani graduates For the socio-cultural perceptions such as media motivation, respect & status depicts significant in Chinese but nonsignificant in Pakistani graduates current status of education, expected degree (undergraduates, graduates to postgraduates) and major subject in agriculture denotes significantly affects entrepreneurial intention for both nation graduates in agribusiness as well.

VI. Conclusion

The impact of media attention and need for achievement on entrepreneurship and was found to influence (EI) in, Chinese but not in Pakistani for agribusiness, on the one hand, the fear of failure (risk perception) was found to influence entrepreneurial intention (EI) significantly affects entrepreneurial intention only in Pakistani students but not

statistically significant in Chinese graduates whereas determinants of self-efficacy and entrepreneurial network factors were found in Chinese but not in Pakistani graduates,

According to the result of this study, in order to enhance entrepreneurial activities in both nations graduates, It can be inferred that because in Pakistani, the number of necessity-driven entrepreneurs is greater than opportunity-driven entrepreneurs because Pakistani graduates mostly dependent on government for job seeking only and their family to choose their career decision to have no choice to work and seeking for the jobs in government sector, in agribusiness firms as a result of lacking formal education and professional degrees.

Further, the media can also play an important role in the promotion of entrepreneurship by publishing and telecasting interviews of successful entrepreneurs. In order to enhance entrepreneurial societies, integrated marketing communication and public media should be considered as one of the important tools to enhance entrepreneurial intention. Hence with more awareness by public media motivation and inspiration, high status and self-respect in society about successful entrepreneurs or entrepreneurial and business management programs can influence people to become more entrepreneurs as job creator rather than the job seeker. Therefore, the policymakers should provide more knowledge about business start-up and management skills in order to turn necessity driven to be opportunity driven entrepreneurs also can push more effort on academic and media as the other strategy to enhance entrepreneurial activity in their countries.

On the psychological side it is important that entrepreneurship must be made socially attractive so that instead of preferring jobs, people take initiatives of launching their own businesses. In both countries generally, people are risk averse while the growth of entrepreneurship has a very strong relationship with the risk-taking ability. Thus, in order to promote entrepreneurship people must be provided proper consultancy and platforms so that they have a sense of security must be made much more effective and communication gap between them in this scenario government has to play a very key role in promoting entrepreneurship among students by making policies in such ways that students have easy access to the initial capital to launch and run their business.

Thus, governments should make commercial and micro-finance banks responsible to extend loans to fresh graduates who want to run their businesses. Further, the ease legal system should be designed by the governments in a way that more and more protection can be given to newly born businesses. Owing to the well-recognized significance of entrepreneurship in the society, it is further proposed that entrepreneurship education should be taught at least to some degree to all students. In this connection, the universities and higher as well.

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